

The Role of International Law in the Irish Legal System- A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

In 1921, the partition of Ireland led to set two parliaments guided mainly by the written constitution. Currently, there are two legal systems in Ireland, directly associated with the common law systems. The Law of Ireland consists of Statute, Common and Constitutional Law however, the Constitutional Law is the highest in the state from which all the other laws derive authority and guidance. Thus, current article also highlights the Irish legislative system and further incorporation of Human Rights Law in the relevant legal infrastructure. We have discussed the extent to which Irish courts are abiding by the European Laws to make the decisions under the European Common of Human Rights under the ECHR Act 2003. Moreover, we also noted how the ECHR Act also makes sure that the Irish legislation respects and grants the rights provisioned by the European Court of Human Rights. Further we have concluded the main points and discussed the limitations accordingly.

Keywords: Irish Law; ECHR; International Law; International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights; European Convention on Human Rights; Civil Rights

1. BACKGROUND:

Irish Law represents one of the oldest surviving legislative systems in Europe, having Proto-Indian-European origins. According to the Irish Act of Union in 18th century until 1921, Ireland was under the rule of the United Kingdom but having separate courts through which appeals could be brought to the House of Lords. Earlier, Irish Law was dominated by Brehons or judges, guided by oral traditions. Some of their judicial decision was also recorded in a written form by Christian clerics. The earliest theory recorded by Christian clerics can be in found in Prologue to the *Senchas Már* which was written in AD 438 (Hopkins, 1966). According to this theory, after a complex case involved Saint Patrick, the Saint ordered the mixing of the Law of Church and the Irish Law. During the process, representatives from each group came forward and recited the laws which were recorded in *Senchas Már* except those conflicting the Church laws. Moreover, the early Irish

Law System was Civil rather than the Criminal Code, concerned primarily with the payment of compensation and the regulation of inheritance, property and contracts. The concept of state-administered laws was completely unfamiliar for the local Irish judiciary. During the Medieval times, this also led to socioeconomic hierarchies and designation of rights and duties (concerning property, relationships between the lords, serfs and their clients) in the Irish society (IHRC, 2010).

In 1921, the partition of Ireland led to set two parliaments guided mainly by the written constitution. Northern Ireland comprises six northeastern counties, located at Stormont on the border of Belfast. Irish court systems were created for both parts of the Island following the final decision and appeal from the House of Lords (Northern Ireland). The Parliament of Northern Ireland had the power to make decisions regarding governance, peace and order but could not legislate on many matters including foreign affairs, copyright and armed forces. These rights were mainly regarded as of great national significance and reserved only for the Westminster. In 1972, Stormont Parliament was abolished during 1999, Northern Ireland stayed under the direct rule of Westminster. After the millennium, Northern Irish Assembly set up under the Good Friday Agreement, however, albeit have always been suspended due to their conflicts with the peace sustainability process (Immigration and Training, 2012).

Currently, there are two legal systems in Ireland, directly associated with the common law systems. The Law of Ireland consists of Statute, Common and Constitutional Law however, the Constitutional Law is the highest in the state from which all the other laws derive authority and guidance (Howie, 2018). Two legal systems in Ireland belong to the common law systems. The country primarily as a common legislative structure containing a written constitution, facilitating democracy based on the Westminster model which is implemented in Great Britain. In this regard, the Irish Constitution gave three powers to the local government: Judicial, Executive and Legislative. Also, the constitution highlighted the difference of power between and vested law-making power in Parliament. The current Irish Law also contains some clauses and principles from the earliest Church laws, adopted mainly by using the method of reasoning, however, there is a conflict regarding the role of these clauses in the existing legal system (IHRC, 2015).

2. THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL LAW IN THE IRISH LEGAL SYSTEM:

Despite Ireland is a dualist state, treaties are not the part of their domestic legal system unless incorporated by the “Oireachtas Eirean” (legislation of Ireland). As the International Laws contain the rules and principles that facilitate the relations between different countries and their dealings with each other, the current constitution says that:

“Ireland would accept the commonly recognized principles of international law as its rule of conduct in its relations with other State”

However, the Supreme Court of Ireland declared this provisions as incapable of conferring on individual rights. This dualist approach enabled the state to ratify and sign the treaties without

consolidating them into the domestic legal system (Cross, 1999). As the domestic laws were not sufficient for the provision of basic rights, international law ensured equal and fair provisions of rights to the Irish citizens. In this regard, the International has direct force on the Irish legislative system without any intermediate implementation to grant the legal force in Ireland. The rule of International Law constitutes equality before the law, equal participation in policy and decision-making process, ensuring the accountability of the judiciary, fairness regarding the implementation of the state policies and basic human rights provision to all (IHRC, 2015). Under the International Rule of Law, Article 29.1 to 29.3 of the Irish constitution contains peaceful negotiations concerning international conflicts. This made Ireland an integral part of several Human Rights conventions and treaties, including:

1. International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)
2. European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR)
3. International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)

2.1 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR):

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights is created following the Character of the United Nations. It constitutes that the recognition of all the human family rights directly relies on peace, freedom and justice in the world. ICCPR recognizes that these rights directly derive from the inherent dignity of human (Reichert, 2004). Ireland ratified ICCPR in 1989 and signed the treaty to abide by its legal standards. Under the ratification, Ireland was asked to adopt the measures and laws to protect the civilians especially the vulnerable ones (Women, disable, immigrants, children). For this purpose, the Irish Human Rights Commission (IHRC) in joint efforts with the ICCPR frequently monitors and reports the relevant Human Rights provisions in the country (Rooney, 2021).

In 2014, IHRC along-with UNHRC and ICCPR inspected Irish legal system regarding the effect of austerity, minority rights, violence against women, abortion rights, people with disability, immigrants' rights, rights of the immigrant children, the right to life and criminal justice system. However, in Ireland, ICCPR has yet not been incorporated with the domestic law but the Irish Human Rights Commission (IHRC) prioritized the cooperation of international human rights bodies to monitor human rights practices and government proceedings (United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2019). Under ICCPR guidance, IHRC ensured that the state made progressive improvements concerning Human Rights by building new prisons. IHRC also raised many concerns regarding overcrowded prisons, physical health of the inmates and freedom of expression. These initiatives guaranteed the solution of overcrowded prisons, violence against children and women, disable and minority rights. Under ICCPR, IHRC is introducing new policies that are influential and can have long-lasting effects (Landman, 2005).

2.2 European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR):

There are four basic sources of law (European law, constitution, case law and legislation), the European Law as the fourth primary source of legislation, is one of the highest-ranking sources in Ireland. Where the international law conflicts the Irish law, the law prevails (UNHR, 2007). As stated:

“No provision of this Constitution invalidates laws enacted, acts done or measures adopted by the State, before, on or after the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon, that is necessitated by the obligations of membership of the European Union referred to in subsection 5° of this section or the European Atomic Energy Community, or prevents laws enacted, acts done or measures adopted by Irish Constitution”

- (i) Said by European Atomic Energy Community, European Union or institutions thereof,*
- (ii) the European Communities or European Union existing immediately before the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon, or institutions thereof, or*
- (iii) bodies competent under the treaties referred to in this section, from having the force of law in the ststae.*

Under the ECHR Act 2003, Irish courts are abiding by the European Laws to make the decisions under the European Common of Human Rights. The ECHR Act also makes sure that the Irish legislation respects and grants the rights provisioned by the European Court of Human Rights. Therefore, the Irish legislative system restricted to take account of the judgment by of the ECHR, even if it involves the countries other than Ireland (Marks & Marks, 2016). The ECHR protects several human Rights and the fundamental freedoms in Ireland including Right to freedom from torture, right to privacy and family life, rights to freedom from torture, right to liberty and security, right to freedom from torture and ill-treatment, right to liberty and security, right to the fair trial and others (UNHR, 2007). The European Convention on Human Rights was integrated into the Irish Constitutional laws during 2003. The articles 2 to 5 contain the mixing of ECHR in Irish laws as mentioned:

Section 2: All the courts are obligated to ensure the compatibility of the Irish law with the European Convention on Human Rights

Section 3: It is a statutory obligation on “every organ of the State” to act under the provisions highlighted by ECHR. This is equally obligatory on Public and Civil servants in how the decisions may influence the civilians and their rights

Section 4: It provides that the Courts will take “judicial notice” of the case of the law of the ECHR. In simple terms, a person is allowed to take appeal to ECHR once his case is dismissed from the local court.

Section 5: Contains the possibility regarding “declaration of incompatibility”. In other words, the local court may consider the incompatibility of the State’s obligation under the European Convention on Human Rights.

Therefore, incorporating ECHR into Irish law, many legal developments took place i.e., immigration laws, family laws, criminal laws and the others. Although critics raised many concerns regarding the compatibility of the Irish laws, certain developments in the ECHR also modified the Irish legislative system resulting in basic Human Rights provision in Ireland (Hopkins, 1966; IHRC, 2010).

2.3 International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)

International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights was ratified in the United Nations General Assembly in 1966. This treaty works to grant the economic, social and cultural rights (Chore, 2002). These rights mainly involve labour rights, right to education, rights to an adequate living standard and right to health. In Ireland, ICESCR has yet not been incorporated with the domestic law and the Irish Law Reform Commission is considering the incorporation of ICESCR. In February 2014, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights strongly recommended the Irish legislation to progressively realize social, economic and cultural rights, subject to maximum available resources and that this duty is mandatory for all the local Irish courts. Although International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights has yet not been incorporated, Irish Human Rights Commission (IHRC) is proposing Human Rights provision under ICCPR (Global Citizenship Commission, 2016).

ICCPR in Ireland encourages equality, non-discrimination, equal rights for men & women to enjoy economic and social rights, the right to work, labour rights (forced labour), the right to social security, the rights to the protection of the family, children and the mother, the right to education and mental health for the children (United High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), 2017). For this purpose, in 2015 the United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights examined Irish laws providing basic rights highlighted by ICCPR. On June 22nd, 2015 the committee presented their report emphasizing the quick ratification of the austerity and make effective policies regarding pre-crisis level funds for the common man. The committee also made suggestions for the Irish Human Rights Commission (IHRC) to guide the public on how to realize their rights in the domestic context. Moreover, IHRC is also waiting for the decision to incorporate the ICESCR with the domestic law to ensure human socioeconomic and cultural rights provision in a subtle manner IHRC (Krause, 2019).

3. CONCLUSION:

In this article, we briefly discussed the role of International law in the Irish legislative system. As under the rule of international law, equality, equity, non-discrimination and peace are the basic human rights, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), European Convention

on Human Rights (ECHR) and International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), all are playing the significant role to ensure the provision of equal rights to all. The incorporation of European law is bringing significant outcomes as it has become an integral part of the Irish constitution. Similarly, the influence of ICCPR and ICESCR is also prominent even though, both laws have yet not been incorporated with the domestic law. In this regard, the Irish Human Rights Commission (IHRC) is working under both organizations to ensure human rights provisions to all without any discrimination of colour, creed, race and ethnicity (Sutto, 2019).

3.1 Study Limitations and Recommendations:

The current study provided a brief yet comprehensive review of the incorporation of the Human Rights Laws in the Irish law. However, it also contains some primary limitations: First, this study involves only Irish legal system that makes the generalizability questionable. Second, this study has no certain methodological grounds. Third and the final limitation involves finite time and resources, when adding human subjects could bring even more fruitful insights. The researcher suggests more studies especially highlighting the international human rights laws and their role in local legislation in the developing countries to find out even more detailed results.

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